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Author	Mélanie HENNART & Sylvain BRISSE
Other contributors	Alexis CRISCUOLO
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D-PHD16-4.4

An inheritance algorithm to provide backwards compatibility of MLST groups with 7-gene MLST identifiers

Extract from the preprint article:

A dual barcoding approach to bacterial strain nomenclature: Genomic taxonomy of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains | bioRxiv.

Melanie Hennart, Julien Guglielmini, Martin C.J. Maiden, Keith A. Jolley, Alexis Criscuolo, Sylvain Brisse. bioRxiv 2021.07.26.453808;

doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.07.26.453808>

In order to attribute to each sublineage (SL) and clonal group (CG), an identifier that would maximally reflect the widely adopted 7-gene ST identifier of the corresponding isolates, a set of naming rules were developed that prioritized the most abundant ST observed among isolates of each group. The formalization of the algorithm is given in supplementary appendix Nomenclature inheritance algorithm, and its implementation as a Python script is provided at <https://gitlab.pasteur.fr/BEBP/inheritance-algorithm>. Here the process for the CG level is described, but the algorithm was also applied to the SL level. Briefly, the data (e.g., a list of CG-ST pairs) can be formalized as a bipartite graph, in which each CG and ST are nodes, and each non-empty CG-ST intersection is an edge. The weight of each edge is equal to the number of isolates sharing the corresponding CG and ST identifiers. Based on this representation, the algorithm will consist of following all edges in the input graph, in the order of decreasing weight. The approach prioritizes the most frequent ST/CG pairs of isolates, *i.e.*, those that are predominant in the dataset and thus naturally transfers to the CG nomenclature, the identifiers of the highest frequency STs. Rules were implemented to treat the cases of equality of representation of two or more STs connected to the same CG. Once all edges were removed from the graph, it may be that some CGs were not named, for example, because the identifier of their unique corresponding ST was already attributed to another CG. For these orphan CGs, iteratively, the initiated identifier at 10000 to highlight identifiers that were attributed with no reference to 7-gene MLST identifiers, plus one.

Nomenclature inheritance algorithm

In order to attribute to each clonal group (CG), an identifier that would maximally reflect the widely adopted 7-gene ST identifier of the corresponding isolates, we developed a set of naming rules that prioritize the most abundant ST observed among isolates of each CG, as well as some supplementary rules in case of ties. This algorithm is summarized below, whereas an example is given in **Figure 1**.

Definitions and notations

Let $G = (U, V, E)$ be a weighted bipartite graph where:

- U is a set of clonal groups (CG) inferred from a cgMLST scheme
- V is the set of sequence types (ST) induced by a MLST scheme
- E is the set of edges $\{u, v\}$ with $u \in U$ and $v \in V$
- $w(\{u, v\})$ is the weight of the edge $\{u, v\}$, *i.e.*, the number of isolates inside $u \cap v$

Let $L(v)$ be the label associated to node v (*i.e.*, the ST identifier), and $L(u)$ the one to determine for u (*i.e.*, the CG identifier).

Let $d_G(v)$ be the degree of a node v inside the graph G , *i.e.*, the number of edges incident to node v .

Let $s(u) := \sum_{v \in V} w(\{u, v\})$ be the size of u , *i.e.*, the number of strains belonging to the CG u .

Let $\Gamma(G)$ be the edge-induced subgraph of a graph G defined by the edge(s) of maximal weight in G .

Let $\Delta_G(u)$ be the set of nodes v that are joined to u inside the graph G and of minimum degree, *i.e.*,

$$\Delta_G(u) := \{v' \in V : \{u, v'\} \in E, d_G(v') = \min_{\{u, v\} \in E} d_G(v)\}.$$

Algorithm

- (a) ◦ $\lambda := \max_{v \in V} L(v)$
- (b) ◦ **while** $E \neq \emptyset$
 - do**
 - (c) ◦ **for each** connected component $G = (U', V', E')$ of $\Gamma(G)$
 - do**
 - (d) ◦ **if** $U' = \{\mu\}$
 - then**
 - (e) ◦ $v := \operatorname{argmin}_{v \in V'} L(v)$
 - else**
 - (f) ◦ $U'' := \operatorname{argmin}_{u' \in U'} s(u')$
 - (g) ◦ **if** $U'' \neq \{\mu\}$
 - then**
 - (h) ◦ $\mu := \operatorname{argmin}_{u'' \in U''} L(u'')$
 - (i) ◦ $v := \operatorname{argmin}_{v \in \Delta_G(\mu)} L(v)$
 - (j) ◦ $L(\mu) := L(v)$
 - (k) ◦ removing μ and v from G , as well as nodes v such that $w(\{\mu, v\}) = w(\{\mu, v\})$
 - (l) ◦ **for each** $\mu \in U$
 - do**
 - (l) ◦ $\lambda := \lambda + 1$
 - (m) ◦ $L(\mu) := \lambda$

Figure 1. Step-by-step illustration of the taxonomic inheritance algorithm

Given 12 hypothetical clonal group (CG, named A-L) and 16 sequence types (ST, labelled from 1 to 16), a weighted bipartite graph G is shown, as well as the use of G to label the CG based on their relation to their related ST. For each step illustration, the corresponding lines of the algorithm pseudo-code (see SupMat) are specified (bottom of each sub-figure).

Figure 1. (continued)

$\Gamma(G)$

(c), (d), (e) and (j)

Figure 1. (continued)

(i)

Figure 1. (continued)

$\Gamma(G)$

(c), (d), (e) and (j)

Figure 1. (continued)

(i)

Figure 1. (continued)

$$\Gamma(G)$$

(c), (d), (e) and (j)

Figure 1. (continued)

(i)

Figure 1. (continued)

$\Gamma(G)$

$L(E) = 8$

(c), (f), (i) and (j)

Figure 1. (continued)

(i)

Figure 1. (continued)

$$\Gamma(G)$$

(c), (d), (e) and (j)

Figure 1. (continued)

$\Gamma(G)$

$L(K) = 16$

(c), (f), (h), (i) and (j)

Figure 1. (continued)

(i)

Figure 1. (continued)

$$\Gamma(G)$$

(c), (f), (h), (i) and (j)

Figure 1. (continued)

(i)

Figure 1. (continued)

$$\Gamma(G)$$

(c), (d), (e) and (j)

Figure 1. (continued)

Figure 1. (continued)

$$\lambda = 16$$

$$L(C) = 17$$

$$L(G) = 18$$

$$L(L) = 19$$

(a), (l), (m) and (n)